

RURAL WOMEN EMPOWERMENT THROUGH SCALING UP “SRI REJEKI” CASAVA HOME INDUSTRY IN PLUNTURAN PONOROGO

Y.B. Agung Prasaja. ; IGN. Anom Maruta

Universitas 17 Agustus 1945 Surabaya

agungprasaja@untag-sby.ac.id; anommaruta@untag-sby.ac.id

ABSTRACT

Many rural women have started developing their own businesses. As the impact it is expected that women are able to create new jobs and increase their own income as well as the village economy. Innovation and optimalization of agricultural products contribute great potential improving for rural women economy. In order to scaling up rural women’s business potentials, It is important to provide education and training in product development, design and business management. They need to have the opportunity to manage the production and market their products widely, both through offline and online platforms, and range from local, regional and international exhibitions. They will have opportunities to produce bigger quantities and better prices, furthermore increasing their income and welfare. The example of rural women empowerment is a micro business in sesame-casava crips produced by Ibu Sri Farida -the owner of Micro business “SRI REJEKI” of Plunturan in Ponorogo East Java. She has produced the casava crips since there are huge casava farming in her village. Sri Rejeki crips micro business has got 2023 community service program from Universitas 17 Agustus 1945 Surabaya, to scaling up the business by implementing effective boiling technology of casava dough for better process and higher capacities.

Keywords: *Effective, Technology, Women, Villager, Agriculture, Startup, Finance*

INTRODUCTION

Women's direct roles in society include work as educators, doctors, economic experts, and preachers, etc. Culturally all institutions recommend that women's activities outside the home should not compromise their main duties as a wife and mother. Women are like schools, if they are educated well it means they have prepared a nation well. The woman with her left hand rocks the cradle and her right hand holds the world . Women are the pillars of the country.

Women are figures who are role models for a generation, so they must be prepared carefully to lead to change. Women will not be able to take care of the household or society with adequate intellectual and ethical knowledge. In fact, Islam pays great attention to women and places them in a position of honour. Women have an important role that cannot be ignored. There are many roles for women in family life, economics, politics, socio-culture, as well as in education and religion. As a member of society, when a woman sees that her community is experiencing a disruption in stability or is affected by disease, she must immediately find a way to overcome it. In fact, under certain conditions, women are required to enter society, for example, there must be women who work as doctors to serve the needs of women.

One of the obstacles for Indonesian women is the contradiction between career and family. It's as if women are forced to choose career or family. If you choose a career, working conditions in Indonesia often do not support the role of a mother. Generally, in offices and companies, working hours are set from morning to evening. As a result, female workers cannot fulfill their children's primary needs, such as breastfeeding. Reluctantly, he entrusted his child to a baby sitter or maid. In the first years of age, a child really needs attention, affection and caress from a mother (Vizheh et al. 2021). In psychology, it is explained that the first years of a child's life are a period of great dependence on a child from his mother. If children's needs are not met, children will tend to experience a crisis of self-confidence. Meanwhile, if a woman takes the second option, namely choosing family and leaving her career, she will feel that all her hard work, for example studying, has been wasted.

In other words, career women in Indonesia generally face a big dilemma, which can only be solved if the government steps in to provide facilities that give women the opportunity to continue having a career while simultaneously carrying out their duties as a mother. By paying attention to the events that occur in the country, it is not true that women are positioned as second class human beings. What must be done is how to position women fairly and equally in politics, because in reality many men are no better than women, but most women are seen as weak parties when entering the political realm(Yuhan, R. J., & Monika 2020). This view is certainly unfair to women, because it must be removed.

In this condition, women who are aware have the duty to enlighten and remind their brothers and sisters of the roles and duties that women must carry out, both through approaches and training. This task will be successful if it is carried out by fellow women, because of the equality of women who have emotional strength, reason, and because women know how each other feels. Generally, women tend to be sensitive to their surrounding environment. The women's movement needs to maintain an open mind, be ready to listen, dialogue and negotiate with various groups in society (Dewi, Eliyana, and Anwar 2022). The problems faced by village women in the fields of socio-economics, education, health and employment opportunities mostly stem from injustice, exclusion and marginalization. But now, the involvement of village women has increased. Various fields of micro sectors such as handicrafts, food and beverages, and services are becoming an inspiration for women In rural areas.. Entrepreneurial potential elevation done by rural women requires comprehensive support (Rathee and Yadav 2018).

Local governments, non-governmental organizations, higher education need to provide training, mentoring, and access to markets for rural women who want to start their own businesses.

The existence of women in Plunturan Village, which is the location of this program, is that women in Plunturan have equal positions with men. The role of women play a role in occupying the motor for the social positions ranging from various institutions in the village. Although society of Plunturan has an egalitarian character in terms of position individuals can be equal, because their social history does not have a royal history like other ethnic groups, where the royal pattern has developed a paternalistic character the strong one. The role of women in all aspects of development is sufficient felt, starting from participating in the construction of village facilities, maintaining village security, PKK in empowering families, and so on. Only the problem is in the village regarding this role, it is actually a bit of a deviation from the traditions of Plunturan women, namely their role in village leadership is seen as lacking, such as the lack of women in positions those in the village, lack positions in the village apparatus (Kholif and Elfarouk 2014). This becomes interesting to study because of changes in society ignoring the role of women, so it is necessary to find the roots the problem.

Talking about women, quite a few studies show that women and children are still classified as vulnerable groups who often experience various problems, such as poverty, natural disasters, conflict, violence, and so on. This does not only happen in Indonesia, but also in other countries throughout the world. Even in the current era of emancipation, women are often considered a second class (subordinate) group so that they do not have equal rights with men. Women are considered only competent in carrying out work related to household affairs. Women can become strategic actors in development (Tiwari and Malati 2023). Not only development in villages, but also national development that can change the lives of Indonesian people to become better and more prosperous.

As time went by, women began to rise and succeeded in proving that their existence was worthy of being taken into account. The intelligence and expertise of Indonesian women, in particular, can no longer be underestimated because they have contributed to development. Meanwhile, regarding efforts to empower women in the economic sector, the creative industry is the answer (Soharwardi and Ahmad 2020). Women have succeeded in dominating labour absorption in the creative industry sector. Women's capacity to think intelligently, be able to secure funds for the family, and invest in productive fields is very potential and real. There is no need to question that women not only have potential, but are actually able to contribute.

MICRO BUSINESS “ SRI REJEKI” AS WOMEN'S PARTICIPATION IN FAMILY ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Steps that can be taken to strengthen women's participation in village development include encouraging gender equality in education, providing skills training and education, developing policies that support women's participation, building social networks and support, and providing financial and technical support. The desire to help husbands in improving the family economy for women today is not difficult. Women gained the freedom to work to help their husbands in increasing family income (Arshad 2023). Women do everything from gardening, farming, trading to factory workers to be able to meet their family's needs. What is no less important is that homework is done together by all family members so that all activities

can be carried out, whether working outside the home, school or domestic work, as expected of the family.

In reality, there are still many women, especially housewives, who do not have access to more roles in society. Access in this era of modernity is intended for people who can manage business opportunities well that combine elements of modernity in accordance with current developments (Dr. Amardeep Bajpai 2022). The use of modern technology cannot be avoided to support the business being managed. Therefore, women are hampered from taking on more roles such as working and starting a business.

Increased income will affect a family's economy. In this case, women as the player in small innovative business have a fairly high status in the family economy. Women who choose to work to earn money will carry out dual roles as housewives and working women. There are several reasons why women work. Women have a reason when they earn a living, that reason is to fulfill household needs. The husband's income, which is deemed insufficient, motivates women to work to earn wages so that the family's needs can be met.

Income in the form of money is usually obtained every day after he works. By working, women hope that there will be changes in their family's lives. Some women work in the home industry because home industry is expected to be able to provide and open employment opportunities for the women themselves and their households. Women who want to work need at least some form of empowerment, especially in terms of skills and insight into the world of work (Franco and Kumar 2016).

MICRO BUSINESS “ SRI REJEKI” AS MANIFESTATION OF WOMEN ROLE IN ECONOMY OF RURAL AREAS

A concrete example of the role of women in village development is Plunturan Village. In Plunturan, women have been actively involved in various development initiatives that have improved the quality of life of the residents of the village as a whole. Women also take strategic steps in diversifying their products. Data shows that female micro business actors are more agile in varying and changing sectors, locations or products, compared to male business actors. Women are important agents for driving economic growth. If women are given equal access, especially in the digital economy and financial access, then this can not only improve economic prosperity and prevent families from poverty, but also help grow the nation's economy (Tripathi, Bansal, and Bansal 2022). "For this reason, synergy, collaboration between all parties, and cooperation with various countries, are very important to ensure that the digital economy can be accessed by all women, especially in Indonesia, in order to create gender equality and financial inclusion.

Women's participation in achieving higher access is increasingly needed in rural region, such as access to digital-based skills and careers; access to digital-based entrepreneurship; and access to leadership in the digital economy in both the private and public sectors. Creative economy-based women's empowerment is an effort to increase knowledge, skills, attitudes and economic income. The development of the creative economy through the use of farming products into valuable business opportunities has proven that some of them have started selling to several local customers who are interested in alternative food products (Papadimitriou, Mylonas, and Frangakis 2022). They have also learned to see the potential of waste in their region or area that can be utilized.

The role of women in economic and business development is very important and continues to grow along with social and cultural changes. Some of the main roles of women in this context involve:

1). Women act as members of the labour market. They not only act as workers but also as leaders at various levels of the organization. 2). Entrepreneurship, by becoming increasingly active in entrepreneurship and the creation of small and medium enterprises. Later they can found new companies, create jobs, and contribute to local and national economic growth. 3). Education and Skills, by increasing women's education and skills, supporting increased work capacity and innovation in various economic sectors. 4). Sustainable and Social Business, women can be involved in sustainable business and social projects that aim to have a positive impact on society and the environment. They tend to pay more attention to sustainability aspects in business decision making. 5). Economic Empowerment, women's economic empowerment programs, such as skills training, access to capital, and business support, can help increase the role and contribution of women in the economy.

THE IMPACT OF MICRO BUSINESS “ SRI REJEKI” ON WOMEN'S ROLE IN PLUNTURAN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

The role of women in village development has a positive impact on society, such as increasing family income, reducing poverty, increasing access to education, improving health, preserving the environment, and improving the overall quality of life. Rural women are playing key models for achieving the transformational economic, environmental and social changes. Limited access to credit, health care and education are obstacles faced by women accompanied with many challenges they face, which are aggravated by the global food and economic crises and climate change. Empowering rural women is important not only to the well-being of individuals, families and rural communities, but also to overall economic productivity, given women's large presence in the agricultural workforce in many rural areas (Arshad 2023).

The processing of crackers carried out by Mrs. Sri Farida is still done traditionally. The equipment used does not comply with standards for the food industry. This is proven by the peeled cassava washing tool in the form of a large tub filled with water, the peeled cassava is put in, then washed manually with hands and feet. In order for the cassava to be clean it has to be washed one by one so it takes a long time, even though the process of grating the cassava uses a machine so it can be done more quickly, the drying process is still done by relying on sunlight so the possibility of exposure to dirt and dust from being dried in the sun is not controlled. under the sun with a braided base, and during the rainy season Mrs. Sri Farida cannot dry it because there is no sunlight. The impact is that crackers that have been sliced become mouldy and give off a stale smell so that the quality becomes low. Other problems identified include hygiene and Sanitation during the processing process is not paid attention to, which carries the risk of contamination of the crackers produced, there is a lot of liquid waste left over from pressing cassava, cassava cracker craftsmen do not carry out good business management and administration, as well as stagnant business conditions due to the lack of product diversification and not developing marketing areas. As an effort to resolve this problem, the Universitas 17 Agustus 1945 Surabaya service team has programmed to carry out training and assistance to partner to organize an activity program to introduce innovative technology for processing cracker dough using a steam system steamer and a drying machine

fuelled by wood waste or firewood which is abundantly available in the area (Tiwari and Malati 2023). Mrs. Sri Farida's place of business in Plunturan village.

CONCLUSION

The important role of women in village development must not be ignored. In Plunturan village, women have proven that their participation brings positive change to the local community. However, there are still challenges and obstacles that need to be overcome so that women can play a full role in village development. Support from the government and village communities is very important in creating an environment that allows women to contribute optimally. By strengthening women's participation, villages can achieve sustainable progress and prosperity for their entire community.

The resilience and capability of women in driving the creative economy entrepreneurial sector cannot be separated from the unique characteristic factors that are generally inherent in women. One of the characteristics that drives women's success in this field includes self-confidence, ambition, enthusiasm, humility, willingness to learn, ownership of target goals, assertiveness, hardworking nature, courage and persistence. Indeed, this character is not exclusively owned by women. However, women tend to be more able to display transformational traits through this character in order to form networks or relationships with other people. This transformational characteristic is important to realize good group performance.

Socioeconomically, women are usually more oriented towards service quality, cultural values and business development aspects. Women are also adept at working independently and adapt easily, both in their capacity as business founders, employees and decision makers. This is a required criterion in the creative industry. In the context of entrepreneurship, women have the power of innovation which is able to create prosperity and employment opportunities. Feminine values in women can also form a unique leadership model, tending to be more sensitive and cooperative, and this is important for creating a balanced work environment.

Changes in the global economy, coupled with the characteristics of women, have contributed to changing the status of women, no longer limited to the domestic sphere, but also taking part outside the home, in the workplace, and building and running businesses. The intelligence and expertise of rural women in particular can no longer be underestimated because they have contributed to development. It is through the creative industry sector that women's empowerment can be implemented very well and have an impact on the survival of society and increase dignity as women. Women are no longer considered only below men, but are able to compete. This is a strategic way to change the paradigm of human resource development (women) to prioritize gender equality.

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